

INFLUENCE OF PERSONALITY TRAITS AND SUBSTANCE ABUSE ON ROAD TRAFFIC VIOLATION AMONG COMMERCIAL MOTORCYCLISTS IN KEFFI, NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of personality traits and substance abuse on road traffic violations among commercial motorcyclists in Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted and the respondents consist of a sample of 303 commercial motorcycle riders aged between 20 and 58 years with an average age of 32.72 year. Data was collected through standardized questionnaires consisting of demographic data of the participants a modified version of the Motorcycle Rider Behaviour Questionnaire, the Big Five Inventory (BFI-20) and the World Health Organization's Alcohol Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST). That data were analyzed using regression analysis and Pearson correlation. The results showed that personality traits jointly and significantly predicted road traffic violations [$F(5, 297) = 10.851, R^2 = .154, p < 0.01$], with openness to experience ($\beta = .205, p < 0.01$), extraversion ($\beta = .154, p < 0.01$), agreeableness ($\beta = .189, p < 0.01$), and neuroticism ($\beta = .148, p < 0.05$), while conscientiousness ($\beta = -.140, p < 0.05$) was negatively associated. Substance abuse has significant influence on road traffic violation [$F(1, 301) = 226.815, R^2 = .374, p < 0.01$]. Age was found to have a significant negative relationship with traffic violations ($r = -.260, p < 0.05$), indicating that younger riders engaged in riskier road behaviors than older riders. The study concludes that traffic violations among commercial motorcyclists in Keffi arise from a mix of personal traits, behavioral habits like substance use, and demographic factors such as age. The study recommends among others that, the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), working with the Nasarawa State government, should develop targeted behavioral programs that match the personality profiles most linked to risky riding.

Keywords: Personality, Traffic violation, substance Abuse, Commercial motorcyclists.

Introduction

Globally, traffic laws are designed to regulate the conduct of road users, protect lives and property, and promote orderly movement. However, in practice, many road users fail to comply with these regulations. According to Marti-Belda et al. (2019) and Hagang et al. (2021), traffic violations such as over-speeding, ignoring signals, reckless overtaking, and driving under the influence of alcohol or drugs are among the leading causes of road crashes worldwide. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2018) estimates that about 1.25 million people die annually from road accidents, while several million others sustain serious injuries. Nearly half of these deaths occur among young people between 15 and 44 years of age, a group that represents the most productive segment of the global population.

In developing countries such as Nigeria, the problem of road traffic violations and accidents is even more serious. Weak enforcement of traffic laws, poor road conditions, and negative driving attitudes all contribute to the high rate of road crashes. According to Sumaila (2013), Nigeria has one of the highest rates of road traffic fatalities in Africa. Although the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) and other enforcement agencies have worked hard to promote

discipline on the roads, violations remain widespread. Afolabi et al. (2025) and Emenike and Akpa (2017) note that despite the presence of traffic regulations, violations such as overloading, speeding, and the use of mobile phones while driving continue to occur frequently across the country.

In urban centers like Keffi, in Nasarawa State, the situation is particularly concerning because of the large number of commercial motorcyclists popularly known as Achaba who dominate the transport system. Commercial motorcycles have become the most common means of transport in Keffi, largely because they are cheap, fast, and easily accessible. Umaru (2013) reported that more than 90 percent of Keffi residents depend on motorcycle transport for their daily movement. Unfortunately, these motorcyclists have been found to contribute significantly to road accidents and general traffic disorder in the area. Many of them are involved in risky and illegal driving behaviors such as over-speeding, dangerous overtaking, carrying more than one passenger, and riding without helmets or licenses (Obadeji et al., 2020).

Research has shown that motorcycles are involved in more accidents per kilometer traveled than cars, and that riders are several times more likely to die in a crash than car drivers (Adogu et al., 2009; Makanjuola et al., 2007). Human error is the major cause of most of these accidents, accounting for over 80 percent of cases (Olasinde & Oluwadiya, 2022). This highlights the need to understand the psychological and behavioral characteristics that influence how individuals behave on the road.

One of the most important psychological factors that has been linked to road behavior is personality. The Five-Factor Model (FFM) of personality describes five broad traits that shape human behavior. They are: openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism (Anglim & O'Connor, 2019; Soto, 2018). These traits have been found to influence how people perceive and respond to rules, risks, and stress. For example, conscientious individuals are usually careful, organized, and law-abiding, while those low in conscientiousness tend to act impulsively and disregard rules. Similarly, agreeable individuals are cooperative and compliant, while those low in agreeableness may be hostile and aggressive. Neurotic individuals are often anxious, emotional, and unstable, which may lead to poor judgment when driving.

Empirical studies have supported the influence of these traits on driving behavior. Luo et al. (2023) and Romero et al. (2019) found that conscientiousness and agreeableness were associated with safer driving, while neuroticism was linked with risky and aggressive behavior on the road. In Nigeria, Akinniyi et al. (2019) reported that extraversion, agreeableness, and conscientiousness significantly predicted safe driving behavior among traffic offenders. Similarly, Ucho et al. (2016) found that agreeableness was a strong predictor of compliance with traffic rules among motorcyclists in North-Central Nigeria. However, not all studies have produced consistent results. Shaapera et al. (2024) found that none of the Big Five traits significantly predicted reckless driving among tricycle riders in Borno State, although substance use showed a strong relationship with road violations. This suggests that personality may not act alone but may interact with other behavioral factors, such as substance use or age, to influence driving behavior.

Substance use is another major factor that has been widely linked to road traffic violations. The use of alcohol, cannabis, and other psychoactive substances among commercial motorcyclists is common in Nigeria and has been found to impair judgment and coordination

(Okpalaku, 2016; Gudaji & Dankishiya, 2016). Many riders report using these substances to stay awake, increase alertness, or cope with long hours and stress (Kosen et al., 2020; Obade & Adefolaju, 2017). Unfortunately, these substances distort perception, reduce reaction time, and increase impulsivity, which often leads to risky behaviors on the road.

Empirical findings have confirmed the relationship between substance abuse and traffic violations. Gudaji and Dankishiya (2016) found that substance-using motorcycle riders were more likely to violate traffic rules and be involved in accidents than those who did not use drugs. Obadeji et al. (2020) similarly reported a high rate of road crashes among commercial motorcyclists in Ado-Ekiti, with alcohol and cannabis use emerging as major contributing factors. Mefoh et al. (2018) found that alcohol, cocaine, and amphetamines significantly predicted road rage behavior among Nigerian drivers, while Jørgenrud et al. (2018) observed that cannabis users were twice as likely to be involved in road crashes in Norway. These findings confirm that substance use has both local and global implications for road safety.

Age is another demographic factor that influences road behavior. Younger riders are generally more likely to take risks, violate rules, and drive aggressively compared to older riders (Chang & Yeh, 2007). This difference is often attributed to inexperience, impulsivity, and the influence of peers. Studies in Nigeria have shown that younger motorcyclists tend to overspeed, disobey traffic rules, and carry multiple passengers, while older riders are more careful and law-abiding (Yakubu, 2015). International evidence also supports this trend. Jørgenrud et al. (2018) found that older riders had significantly lower odds of being involved in traffic crashes compared to younger ones.

The theoretical framework for this study is based on Eysenck's Personality Theory and the Five-Factor Model of personality. Eysenck's theory proposes that individual differences in personality are biologically based and that traits such as extraversion, neuroticism, and psychoticism influence behavior through levels of cortical arousal and conditioning. According to the theory, individuals high in extraversion or neuroticism are more prone to risk-taking and antisocial behavior because they have lower levels of internal inhibition. In contrast, individuals with high levels of conscientiousness or agreeableness are more likely to conform to social norms and obey rules. When applied to driving, this means that people with certain personality patterns may be more likely to commit road traffic violations.

Problem Statement

Road traffic violations have become a major public safety concern in Keffi, Nasarawa State, particularly among commercial motorcyclists who constitute a significant proportion of road users. These violations ranging from reckless driving, disregard for traffic rules, overspeeding, and driving under the influence of substances often result in accidents, injuries, and loss of lives (Umaru, 2013). For instance, According to the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), there was 38,619 motorcycle-related crashes in Nigeria, in 2019, with a death rate of 16.1% (FRSC Annual Report, 2019). Motorcycle related injuries have remained as a leading cause of disability and deaths among the young and economically productive groups of population (Olasinde & Oluwadiya, 2022). Motorcycle-related crashes accounted for 57.1% of injuries in patients at the Dalhatu Specialist Hospital in Lafia the State capital (Afolabi et al., 2025). Despite various interventions by traffic management authorities, the frequency of such violations remains alarmingly high (Emenike & Akpu, 2017).

One area that has received limited attention is the psychological and behavioural factors that may contribute to this problem. Specifically, the role of personality traits and substance abuse

influencing risky road behaviours among commercial motorcyclists remains underexplored. The five-factor model of personality which include openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism have been associated with a series of dysfunctional behaviours, ranging from violence to drug abuse and other risky behaviours. However, few studies have investigated motorcycle riders' personality traits (Romero et al., 2019). It is possible that individual differences in certain personality traits may explain individual differences in the level of traffic violation among commercial motorcyclists. For instance, individuals high in neuroticism may exhibit emotional instability, while those low in conscientiousness may show poor impulse control and these are factors that could predispose them to violate traffic rules.

Furthermore, substance abuse is known to impair judgment, slow reaction time, and reduce self-awareness, thereby increasing the likelihood of road traffic violations (Kosen et al., 2020). Among commercial motorcyclists in, the use of substances such as alcohol, marijuana, and other stimulants is reportedly highly prevalent, often justified as a means of coping with the demands and stress of the job (Anigwe et al., 2024; Gudaji & Dankishiya, 2016). Commercial motorcyclists were reported responsible for up to sixty percent of road traffic accidents associated with substance abuse.

There is a paucity of empirical studies that examine the combined influence of personality traits and substance abuse on traffic rule violations in this population and this gap in knowledge hinders the development of targeted interventions aimed at reducing such violations and improving road safety.

Research Hypotheses

1. Personality traits will significantly influence road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi.
2. Substance abuse will significantly influence road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi.
3. There will be a significant relationship between age and road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi.

METHOD

Research Design

This study adopted the cross-sectional survey research design. The cross-sectional study aims at collecting information on certain variables in a study population at one point in time and gives an opportunity to get an overview of the issues involved in the study. This method was considered most relevant in eliciting response on the influence of personality traits and substance abuse on road traffic violation among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

The study was conducted among commercial motorcycle operators who are operating within Keffi Local Government Area. The majority of the commercial motorcycle operators are not registered under any association and as such there is lack of data concerning the number of commercial motorcyclists operating in Keffi. However, an earlier study estimates their population to be about 1,500 (Umaru, 2013). The sample size was determined using Taro

Yamantia formula based on this estimated population of 1,500 as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$
 Where N is total population; 1,500 and e is tolerable error 0.5%

$$n = \frac{1,500}{1 + 1,500(0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{1,500}{1 + 1,500(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{1,500}{4.75}$$

$$n = 316$$

Therefore, the study sample consisted of 316 commercial motorcyclists operating in Keffi Town. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the motorcyclists that participated in this study. This method of sampling was chosen as it is best suited for this study considering the nature of the job of the motorcyclists. Most of them are constantly on the move and it will difficult to have access to all of them at the same time. Hence, only those who were available and consented to participate were selected to participate in the study.

Method of Data Collection

The instruments used for the study is a self-report questionnaire consisting of demographic data of the participants and three measures namely an adapted version of the Motorcycle Rider Behaviour Questionnaire (MRBQ) developed by Elliott, et al. (2007), the Big Five Inventory (BFI-20) and the World Health Organization's Alcohol Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST).

The Motorcycle Rider Behaviour Questionnaire (MRBQ) is a structured self-report instrument developed by Elliott et al. (2007) to assess the typical riding behavior of motorcyclists. The original MRBQ contains 43 items each describing a specific riding behavior. These behaviors fall into five broad categories: traffic errors, control errors, speed violations, stunt performance and use of safety equipment. This study made use of an adapted version consisting of 24 items that are suited for the context of the study. Participants are asked to rate how often they engage in each behavior using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = Never to 5 = nearly all the time. Example MRBQ items include: "Exceed the speed limit on a motorway or major road", "Brake too hard on a slippery road" and "Wear brightly colored or reflective clothing". The items are summed up after scoring with higher scores reflecting increased possibility of traffic violation.

The MBRQ have been reported to have a fairly adequate reliability. Sakashita et al (2014) reported Cronbach alpha ranging from 0.47 to 0.81 for the subscales of the MBRQ. Oluwadiya (2010) validated the MBRQ among motorcyclists in Osun State Nigeria and reported an overall Cronbach alpha of 0.526.

The Big Five Personality Inventory (BFI-20) is a brief 20-item instrument developed by Diener and Lucas (2020) to measure personality traits based on the five factor model of personality. The BFI-20 is a shortened version of the 44-item BFI developed by John and Martinez (1988). The BFI-20 consists of 20 items with four of each dedicated to each of the big five personality traits. The items are phrased as self-descriptive statements to which

respondents indicate their level of agreement using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 ("strongly disagree") to 5 ("strongly agree"). Some of the items (6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 15, 16, 17, 18, and 20) are scored in reversed.

The BFI-20 is a reliable and efficient tool for measuring the Big Five personality traits in a concise manner. Regarding reliability, the BFI has shown satisfactory internal consistency across numerous studies conducted in different countries, including the United States, France, Italy, Spain, Canada, Turkey, and Bolivia. Reported Cronbach's alpha values generally exceeded the acceptable threshold of .70, ranging from .73 for Neuroticism to .81 for Extraversion (Fossati et al., 2011; Srivastava et al., 2003). Convergent validity of the BFI has also been demonstrated through comparisons with other well-established personality assessments, such as the NEO-PI-R and the NEO-IPIP. In a study by Soto and John (2017) conducted in the United States, strong correlations were observed between corresponding dimensions of the BFI and the NEO-PI-R, with average correlation coefficients exceeding .70 in both undergraduate and general population samples.

The ASSIST is a validated structured interview that was developed by the World Health Organisation. The test identifies lifetime as well as current use of various substances. The ASSIST consists of eight items. The first 7 items cover ten substances: tobacco, alcohol, Cannabis, cocaine, amphetamine type stimulants, inhalants, sedatives, hallucinogens, opioids and 'other drugs'. Item 1 elicits information about lifetime use of substances. The second item asks about frequency of use during the prior three months. Items 3-5 and 7 elicit information in line with ICD-10/DSMIV diagnostic criteria. Item 6 is about friend or relative's expression of concern about the individual's use of substances. The last item elicits information about non-medical use of drugs by injection. For the current study, only the second item which asks about frequency of use during the prior three months will be used.

The ASSIST has been reported to have good reliability. Humeniuk and Ali (2006) reported that the internal consistency of the ASSIST ranged between 0.66 and 0.89 for substance specific domain scores. It has been validated in Nigeria among a sample of university students and internal consistency of the different domains ranged between 0.77 and 0.94 (Onifade et al., 2014).

Techniques for Data Analysis

Data were analyzed with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The distribution of the participants' demographic characteristics were presented using descriptive statistics. Regression analysis was used to test hypotheses 1 and 2 respectively while Pearson correlation will be used to test hypothesis 3.

Results

A total of 316 questionnaires were administered to the participants to gather data for the study. Out of these, 309 were returned. Six of the returned questionnaires were not properly completed, so they were removed from the final analysis. Hence, the results in this chapter are based on 303 well-completed questionnaires.

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Demographic Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Age (Mean = 32.72)		
30 years and below	145	47.9

31-40 years	81	26.7
41-50 years	63	20.8
51-60 years	14	4.6
Total	303	100.0
Religion		
Islam	177	58.4
Christianity	80	26.4
Other Religion	46	15.2
Total	303	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	191	63.0
Married	96	31.7
Separated/Divorced	16	5.3
Total	303	100.0
Educational Qualification		
Primary School	60	19.8
Secondary School	210	69.3
Polytechnic Diploma/NCE	21	6.9
HND/Bachelors Degree or Higher	12	4.0
Total	303	100.0

Table 4.1 presents the demographic characteristics of the 303 commercial motorcycle riders who participated in the study. The average age of respondents was approximately 32.7 years, with nearly half (47.9 percent) aged 30 years or below. Riders aged 31 to 40 years made up 26.7 percent of the sample, while those aged 41 to 50 years accounted for 20.8 percent. The smallest age group was riders between 51 and 60 years, representing just 4.6 percent of participants. This distribution suggests that the occupation is dominated by young and early middle-aged adults. In terms of religion, a majority of participants identified as Muslim (58.4 percent), followed by Christians (26.4 percent), while 15.2 percent belonging to other faiths. Regarding marital status, the largest proportion of riders were single (63.0 percent), while 31.7 percent were married. A smaller share, 5.3 percent, reported being separated or divorced. Educational attainment among the riders showed that most had completed secondary school (69.3 percent). Nearly one-fifth (19.8 percent) had only primary school education, while smaller proportions reported holding a polytechnic diploma or NCE (6.9 percent) or a higher national diploma/bachelor's degree (4.0 percent).

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the influence of Personality Traits on Road Traffic Violation

DV	Predictors	β	t	Sig.
Traffic violation	(Constant)		4.386	.000
	Openness	.205	3.427	.001
	Conscientiousness	-.140	-2.513	.013
	Extraversion	.154	2.691	.008
	Agreeableness	.189	2.776	.006

Neuroticism	.148	2.559	.011
R		.393	
R ²		.154	
F		10.851**	

Note * = p < .05, ** = p < .01

The results in Table 2 show that, taken together, the five dimensions of personality significantly predicted road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi [F(5, 297) = 10.851, R² = .154, p < 0.01]. The results also indicate that personality traits explained 15.4 percent of the variation in riders' traffic violations. Looking at each trait individually, openness to experience ($\beta = .205$, p < 0.01), extraversion ($\beta = .154$, p < 0.01), agreeableness ($\beta = .189$, p < 0.01), and neuroticism ($\beta = .148$, p < 0.05) all had significant and positive influence on road traffic violations, suggesting that riders high in these traits were more likely to engage in risky or unlawful riding. In contrast, conscientiousness ($\beta = -.140$, p < 0.05) showed a significant negative influence, indicating that more disciplined and organized riders were less likely to commit violations.

Table 3: Regression analysis showing the influence of substance abuse on road traffic violation

Variables	β	t	df	R	R ²	F	Sig.
(Constant)		9.748					
Substance Abuse	.611	15.060	1, 301	.611	.374	226.815	.000

The results presented in Table 3 indicated that substance abuse had a strong and significant positive influence on traffic violations [F(1, 301) = 226.815, R² = .374, p < 0.01], accounting for 37.4 percent of the variation in road traffic violations among the respondents. This finding supports the stated hypothesis that riders who engage in substance use are more prone to unsafe riding behaviour.

Table 4: Summary results of Pearson correlation between age and road traffic violation

Variable	\bar{x}	SD	r	df	Sig.
Age	32.72	9.267			
Traffic violation	62.32	10.283	-260	300	.004

As shown in Table 4, the Pearson correlation results revealed a significant negative relationship between age and traffic violations (r = -.260, p < 0.05). This means that younger riders were more likely to commit violations, while older riders tended to have fewer offenses. Hence, the stated hypothesis was confirmed in this study.

Discussion of Findings

The present study investigated the influence of personality traits and substance abuse on road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

The results show that the dimensions of the big five personality traits have significant joint

influence on road traffic violation among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi. This suggests that personality traits play an important role in explaining why some commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi are more likely to break traffic rules. The fact that all five dimensions of the Big Five personality traits together predict traffic violations means that these psychological traits affect how riders make decisions, take risks, and follow traffic laws. This finding agrees with several previous scholars who also found that personality traits are significant factors that explain how riders as well as drivers adhere to safety regulations (Akinniyi et al., 2019; Kosen et al., 2020; Ucho, et al., 2016). The in contrast with this finding, a related study conducted among commercial tricyclists in Borno by Shaapera, et al. (2024) found that personality traits had no significant influence on reckless driving.

The finding of this study supports Eysenck personality theory of crime, which says that stable traits in a person's temperament and character can influence whether they tend to follow rules or break them. In other words, the way riders think, feel, and react to situations can either lead them toward risky driving or help them stick to safe habits.

Looking at each trait separately, openness to experience, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism were all linked to a higher chance of breaking traffic rules. Unlike this study, Luo et al. (2023) found that agreeableness, and openness were negatively associated with risky and aggressive driving behaviours. Riders high in openness may be more willing to try unfamiliar routes or unconventional riding styles, which could lead to risky actions on the road. Extraverted riders, who enjoy excitement and social interaction, may be more drawn to thrill-seeking or impulsive behaviors. The finding on agreeableness is unusual because in many settings it is linked with cooperation and compliance. For instance, Hussain et al. (2020) multi-country study among drivers in Japan, China, and Vietnam found that agreeableness consistently predicted fewer aggressive driving behaviours across all three countries suggesting that individuals with higher levels of agreeableness are generally more compliant and less hostile in traffic situations. The positive link between neuroticism and violations could be because emotionally unstable riders may react to stress or provocation with aggression or poor judgment, leading to more infractions.

Conscientiousness, on the other hand, had a negative relationship with traffic violations, which matches both theory and common sense including reports from similar studies by several scholars (Akinniyi et al., 2019; Luo et al., 2023). People who are conscientious tend to be organized, disciplined, and careful about the future, making them more likely to follow traffic laws and think before acting. From a social learning theory point of view, these riders may have learned self-control and law-abiding habits early in life from positive role models, which helps them avoid risky behavior on the road.

The findings show that substance abuse is a significant factor in predicting road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi. Specifically, substance abuse was found to have a significant positive influence on substance abuse. In simpler terms, riders who use alcohol, cannabis, or other drugs are more likely to break traffic rules and take dangerous risks on the road than those who do not. This finding echoes several other empirical reports associating substance abuse with road traffic violation (Gudaji & Dankishiya, 2016; Olaniyi, 2020; Mefoh et al., 2018). Furthermore, the study found that substance abuse accounted for 37.4 percent of the differences in traffic violation rates among the motorcyclists in this study. This means that it is not just a small influence but a major cause of unsafe riding in this group. This supports social learning theory, which says people often copy behaviors they see and accept within their social circles. Some of these riders may have seen the substance abuse is commonly prevalent and accepted among their colleagues in the parks and its is viewed as something that boosts alertness or confidence, they may be more likely to use it even though it harms their judgment and slows their reaction times.

There are also practical and social realities explanation behind this finding. Many riders in Keffi face financial pressure to work for long stretches with few breaks in order to meet up their daily financial targets, leading some to take substances to stay awake or boost their energy. Others may use them in social settings, especially in places where roadside bars or gathering spots are part of everyday life. Unfortunately, these substances can reduce focus, slow reflexes, and impair decision-making in busy traffic conditions.

Furthermore, the results showed a significant negative relationship between age and road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi. This finding suggests that, younger riders are more likely to engage in risky or unlawful riding, while older riders tend to break traffic rules less often. This finding agrees with Yakubu (2015) whose study conducted among commercial motorcyclists in Ilorin Kwara State Nigeria found that younger riders are significantly more likely to violate the rule of carrying one passenger per trip. Similarly, Jørgenrud et al (2018) Norwegian study found that increasing age was significantly associated with lower risk of involvement in road traffic accidents. Younger people are often more impulsive, drawn to excitement, and less cautious about risk compared to older riders. As individuals grow older, they usually develop stronger self-control, better planning skills, and a greater awareness of consequences, which can lead to safer driving habits. Practical life factors and experience may also explain this finding. For many younger riders, commercial motorcycling is a quick way to make money, and with fewer financial commitments, they might feel freer to take risks. Older riders, often supporting families or having experienced accidents in the past, tend to value stability and take fewer chances. Physical changes with age such as slower reaction times, reduced stamina, and a different perception of danger may also influence how riders behave on the road.

Conclusion

This study concludes that road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi arise from a mix of personal traits, behavioral habits like substance use, and demographic factors such as age. The findings reveal that riders high in openness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism are more likely to engage in risky riding, whereas conscientiousness acts as a protective factor. Substance abuse is also a significant factor influencing road traffic violation among motorcyclists in Keffi. The study also concludes that there is a significant negative association between age and road traffic violation among commercial motorcyclists in Keffi.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to help reduce road traffic violations among commercial motorcycle riders in Keffi:

First, the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), working with the Nasarawa State government, should develop targeted behavioral programs that match the personality profiles most linked to risky riding.

Second, community-based substance abuse prevention and rehabilitation programs should be introduced, led by local health authorities and non-governmental organizations. These initiatives should combine education and support, informing riders about the dangers of riding under the influence while also offering accessible counseling and rehabilitation for those struggling with dependency.

Third, the Motorcycle Riders Union in Keffi should take an active role in shaping a safer occupational culture through measure such as creating peer mentorship programs, where experienced, safety-conscious riders guide younger members, promoting adherence to traffic laws and discouraging risky maneuvers.

Fourth, road safety campaigns should be tailored to different age groups.

Finally, law enforcement agencies should increase consistent traffic monitoring in Keffi so

Drivers are likely to see the risk of being caught and penalized for violations.

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